

Childhood Obesity: Assessing Parental Knowledge On Obesity Determinants in Hispanic Children Implementing a Culturally Modified Screening Tool

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Background

- ❖ Childhood obesity significantly impacts Hispanic children and adolescents more than any other ethnic group of children.
- ❖ The prevalence of obesity among Hispanic children has risen in the last thirty years, with rates of obesity as high as 21.9% in comparison to the obesity rates of:
 - non-Hispanic blacks (19.5%)
 - non-Hispanic whites (14.7%)
 - non-Hispanic Asian youth (8.6%)

(Ochoa & Berge, 2016)

Problem Statement

There is an underlying need to identify determinants contributing to obesity within the Hispanic family unit by examining associations of bio behaviors, parental attitudes and perceptions of health versus obesity, examine food preferences and eating patterns, and determine level of physical activity.

Purpose

To adapt a well-established general nutritional screening tool addendum and modify it to address the specific needs for the Hispanic family unit that were identified in the literature as significant.

Theoretical Framework

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory Triadic Model (Bandura, 1977).

Review of Literature

- ❖ Multiple root causes have been identified as having adverse effects on children and adolescent obesity, including cultural influence, parental perception, attitudes, and beliefs, fried, fatty foods, sugar-sweetened drinks, snacks, eating larger portion sizes at every meal and decreased physical activity (Boudreau et al., 2013; Rosas et al., 2011).
- ❖ School age Mexican-American boys were deemed overweight as compared to school aged Mexican-American girls by a ratio of 40% to 34% respectively (Sosa, 2012).
- ❖ A mother's lack of knowledge regarding the concept of obesity, including its meaning, importance, causes and consequences, and perceptions on prevention or recognizing barriers will likely affect their probability to engage in preventive behaviors.
- ❖ A traditional factor present in Hispanic families is an underlying belief that children who are larger in size equates with good health (Foster & Hale, 2015; Ochoa & Berge, 2016; Pulgaron et al., 2013).
- ❖ Individual, environmental, and cultural factors coupled with the underlying perceptions of Hispanic parents, the complexity of the sociocultural dynamics signal that culturally appropriate obesity education and interventions are lacking, need further exploration, and require cultural tailoring (Turer et al., 2014).

Discussion

- ❖ The findings revealed an initial critical problem in that the concept of mass body index (BMI) was not understood regardless of language, level of education, or acculturation in Hispanic families (Sosa, 2012; CDC, 2015b).
- ❖ Though the sample size is small, the findings support the need to teach Hispanics on the most basic of obesity concepts, understanding what obesity means, how it's measured, to introduce and/or familiarize Hispanics with alternative and healthier choices, to teach how to incorporate cultural food staples in a healthier form, and to provide guidance and support that will result in meaningful lifestyle changes.

Baseline Habits

Table 1

Baseline Habits: Anthropometric Measures

	N	Range	Mean ± SD
Participants: Child			
Age	13	06 – 17	11.92 ± 3.70
Height	13	50.28 – 67.44	60.04 ± 6.62
Weight	13	82.1 – 204.2	143.04 ± 3.52
BMI	13	94 – 97	96.53 ± 0.87
Participants: Parents			
Average length in the US	13	19-30	22.4 ± 7.94

Table 3

Baseline Habits: Averages

Participants	Percentage* ± SD
Average activity	
Time spent in Physical Activity (hrs/week)	2.23 ± 1.69
Time spent on TV/Video/Media (hrs/week)	3.0 ± 2.31
Time spent outdoors: playing, sports, being active	00 ± 0.00
Average consumption	
Eat fried/Junk/Fast food/servings/week	3.23 ± 1.69
Eat fruits/vegetable/Week	1.92 ± 1.18
Sugary Drinks (8 oz/daily)	4.38 ± 1.75

Methods

- ❖ A literature gap exists in that there is an absence of tools which assess knowledge deficits specific to Hispanic families including the conceptualization of obesity, screening tools, bio-behaviors, socioeconomic status, and normative cultural values.
- ❖ Administer the adapted screening tool to the sample of 13 Hispanic parents of overweight and obese children and adolescents.

Results

- ❖ 93% of respondents did not know what the term BMI meant.
- ❖ 77% of participant parents believed that their children were overweight, but a common theme was an underlying belief that children who are larger in size are viewed as being in good health.
- ❖ Overall the participating children were consuming above-average levels of fast food (3.23 servings/week), sugary beverages (4.38 servings/day), and spent at least 3 hours on screen time.

Nursing Implications

- ❖ An analysis of nationwide provider statistics found that Hispanic children were less likely to receive preventive pediatric obesity counseling during office visits versus other ethnicities.
- ❖ An underlying need to address parental perception of weight and health status, cultural practices, and address knowledge deficits during the primary care visit and encourage regular, follow-up care.
- ❖ Providers should consider interventions that are instilled with cultural values and principles to improve screening, management, and prevention that target the family unit.
- ❖ The DNP role is well suited to collaborate with the multidisciplinary team to screen and develop culturally competent interventions targeting Hispanics.